

Simultaneous Determination of Antimony and Tin by N-Benzoyl-N-Phenylhydroxylamine

M. K. SHIRGUPPI and B. C. HALDAR

Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory, Institute of Science, Bombay-400 032

Manuscript received 16 January 1976; accepted 15 June 1976

A method has been developed for simultaneous determination of Sb and Sn in Type Metal and White Metal using N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine as a precipitating agent. The accuracy for each element is better than 0.6%. Sb(III) can be estimated in the presence of Sb(V).

ANTIMONY is usually determined gravimetrically as antimony trisulphide or antimony tetroxide¹.

The trisulphide method is tedious and time-consuming. Further it does not permit to estimate Sb(III) in the presence of Sb(V). In the second method, the trisulphide obtained by the action of hydrogen sulphide is dissolved and finally ignited to weigh as the tetroxide, Sb₂O₄. The procedure does not seem to have any advantage over the sulphide method and it requires greater care than the latter. Antimony is also precipitated as a gallate² using gallic acid as the precipitant. In this method the temperature should be controlled very carefully. Moreover, the gallate formed is very unstable and Kieft³ has reported that gallic acid decomposes in aqueous solution above 85°. In the pyrogallate method⁴, Bi interferes and pyrogallol being easily oxidisable its solutions are unstable and cannot be preserved for a long period. It is also reported⁵ that *n*-propyl gallate is to be preferred to gallic acid and pyrogallol as an analytical reagent for antimony. The method proposed by Wilson and Lewis⁶ is time-consuming and Bi interferes. Pirtea⁷ and Cardwell and his co-workers⁸ have suggested 8-hydroxyquinoline as a precipitant for antimony. But in Pirtea's method, the precipitate is to be dried exactly at 108°, and in the method proposed by Cardwell *et al.* the solution is to be heated at 70° for 3 hr. In the method proposed by Asmus and Ziesche⁹ using 1,2-dimorpholinoothane as the precipitant for antimony, bromide interferes. Thus, a survey of the literature indicates a lack of selective, fast and accurate method for gravimetric determination of antimony. N-Benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine (BPHA) precipitates antimony(III) quantitatively from 1.5 to 3.0M. HCl solution¹⁰. Further, BPHA does not react with antimony(V) in this range of acid concentration. In the present investigation BPHA has been utilized for the estimation of Sb(III) and analyses of binary mixtures containing (i) Sb(III)+Sb(V) and (ii) Sb(III)+Sn(IV). The method developed has been employed to analyse Type Metal and White Metal.

Experimental

Chemicals: Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Whenever, A.R. grade chemicals were not available, C.P. chemicals were employed after purification. Double distilled water was used for preparing standard solutions. Stock solutions of Sb(III), Sb(V) and Sn(IV) were prepared by standard procedures¹. Aqueous solution of KI (10%), ascorbic acid (1%) and Na₂EDTA (3%) were used in all experiments. A 1% solution of BPHA in acetic acid was employed. The solutions of cations used in interference study were prepared by dissolving their chlorides, sulphates or nitrates. Sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of various anions were used to prepare their solutions.

Antimony was estimated⁴ by titration with 0.1N iodine solution. Tin solution was standardized against standard potassium iodate solution⁴. Solutions of different cations were analysed by procedures described by Vogel⁴. Samples were weighed on a semi-micro balance weighing accurately up to 0.02 mg.

Estimation of Sb(III) using N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine

A 1% solution of BPHA in acetic acid was added to a solution of Sb(III) in 1.5M-3.0M HCl. The white precipitate was allowed to settle for about 2 hr at 5°. It was then filtered through a sintered-bed crucible, washed first with 100 ml of 10% acetic acid and then with 10ml of distilled water, dried at 105°-110° to constant weight and weighed as Sb (C₁₃H₁₀O₂N)₃. This procedure was employed to analyse mixtures of solutions containing Sb(III) (5-40 mg) and Sb(V) (5-100 mg). Sb(III) was precipitated from the mixture by BPHA and it was separated and weighed as mentioned above. A slight excess of 10% KI solution was added to the filtrate and the solution was boiled for about 15 to 20 min to reduce Sb(V) into Sb(III). A solution of ascorbic acid was then added to reduce liberated iodine to iodide. The acidity of the solution was adjusted between 1.5-3.0M with HCl. Sb(III) was

then determined as described earlier. The amount of Sb(V) was calculated from the weight of the precipitate.

Estimation of Sb(III) and Sn(IV) present in a mixture:

To a 1.5–3.0M HCl solution containing 5–10 mg of Sb(III) and 5–40 mg Sn(IV) was added a solution of BPHA to precipitate Sb(III), which was filtered, dried and weighed. Sn(IV) was then determined as $(C_{13}H_{11}O_2N).SnCl_2$ from the filtrate ($pH = 1.5$) using BPHA as reported in the literature⁴.

Results and Discussion

The precipitation of 10.11 mg. Sb(III) with BPHA from 1.5–3.0M HCl solution is quantitative within 1% error. The minimum amount of Sb(III) that could be precipitated quantitatively by this method is found to be 5 mg. in 100 ml. of solution. The following ions do not interfere: chloride, bromide, iodide, carbonate, phosphate, arsenate, borate, nitrate, sulphate, thiosulphate, sulphocyanide, chromate, dichromate, acetate oxalate, Mg(II), Sn(IV), Ca(II), Ba(II), Sr(II) and As(III). The interference of Al(III), Pb(II), Bi(III), Cu(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Cr(III), Fe(II), Fe(III), Mn(II) and Ni(II) can be removed by carrying out the precipitation of Sb(III) in the presence of EDTA. Cyanide can be masked with Zn(II), the excess of which is complexed by adding EDTA. Mercury interferes.

BPHA does not react with Sb(V) in 1.5–3.0M HCl solution and so it can be used successfully for the quantitative separation of Sb(III) from Sb(V). Some typical results shown in Table I indicate that the error in the determination of 5 mg. of Sb(III) does not exceed 0.6% and binary mixtures of Sb(III) and Sb(V) can be analysed successfully by the proposed

method. The values for Sb and Sn in Type Metal and White Metal obtained by following the recommended procedure are in good agreement with the certified values.

Determination of antimony in White metal and Type metal :

About 120–150 mg. of the metal was weighed accurately and dissolved in 20 ml. of aqua regia. The solution was boiled with 15 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid to remove excess nitric acid. The solution was boiled with excess of potassium iodide (200 mg) to reduce Sb(V) into Sb(III). 5 ml. of 10% solution of ascorbic acid were added to reduce iodine to iodide. 2 g. of disodium salt of EDTA were added to mask the other elements (such as Pb, Cu, Fe, etc.) present. The solution was then cooled to 5° and Sb(III) and Sn(IV) were precipitated with BPHA as described earlier.

Precision and accuracy of the method

The precision and accuracy of the method were tested by analysing solutions containing known amounts of Sb. The analyses of 10 samples each containing 10.11 mg of Sb in 100 ml. of solution gave an average value of 10.10 mg, which varied between 10.00 and 10.20 at 95% confidence limit.

The main advantages of the proposed method over other known methods are freedom from the interference by Br⁻ and Bi and that it can be employed to analyse solutions of Sb(III) and Sb(V) or Sn(IV). Moreover, under the experimental conditions employed, the method is selective, rapid and accurate.

References

1. N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., London, 6th Ed., 1962, Vol. I.
2. C. FRESSENIUS, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", J. and A. Churchill, London, 7th Ed., 1900, Vol. II.
3. L. KIEFT and G. C. CHANDLEE, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1936, 8, 392.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co., London, 3rd Ed. 1961.
5. R. A. NASH, D. M. SKAUVEN and W. C. PURDY, *J. Amer. Pharm. Ass.*, 1958, 47, 433.
6. A. D. WILSON and D. T. LEWIS, *Analyt.*, 1963, 88, 585.
7. T. I. PIETEA, *Analyt. Abs.*, 1966, 13, 3517. (*Z. Analyt. Chem.* (in German), 1965, 208, 411).
8. T. J. CARDWELL, F. G. NASOURI, H. H. MCCONNELL and R. J. MAGEE, *Analyt. Abs.*, 1969, 17, 128. (*Austral. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 359).
9. E. ASMUS and D. ZIESCHE, *Analyt. Abs.*, 1966, 13, 4786. (*Z. Analyt. Chem.* (in German), 1965, 210, 177).
10. S. J. LYLE and A. D. SHENDRIKAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1966, 36, 286.

TABLE I

Sample	Amount in mg.		% Error
	Taken	Found	
Sb(III) and Sb(V)	5.00	4.98	-0.4
Sb(III) and Sb(V)	100.00	99.50	-0.5
Sb(III) and Sb(V)	40.00	40.00	0.0
Sb(III) and Sb(V)	5.00	4.97	-0.6
Sb(III) and Sn(IV)	5.05	5.03	-0.4
Sb(III) and Sn(IV)	40.00	40.20	+0.5
Sb(III) and Sn(IV)	10.10	10.11	+0.1
Sb(III) and Sn(IV)	5.00	5.01	+0.2
Type Metal Sb	14.25	14.28	+0.2
Sn	6.81	6.77	-0.6
White Metal Sb	13.63	13.55	-0.6
Sn	5.71	5.69	-0.4